

ILLOCUTIONARY SPEECH ACTS USED BY PRESIDENT FERDINAND R. MARCOS JR. DURING THE 2022 AND 2023 STATE OF THE NATION ADDRESS

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Illocutionary Speech Acts used by President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. during the 2022 and 2023 State of the Nation Address

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine what Illocutionary Speech Acts were employed by President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. in his 2022 and 2023 SONAs, classify the identified Illocutionary Speech Acts with the 5 classifications of Illocutionary Speech Acts according to Searle for accuracy, and assess the data to determine the most dominant Illocutionary Speech Acts used and least used to understand what kind of speaker President Marcos Jr. is. This study used the Discourse Analysis Method grounded in the Speech Act Theory of Austin and Searle by process of analysis, categorization, and assessment. The study focused on the 2022 and 2023 SONAs of Philippine President Ferdinand Marcos Jr. The result of the study is that out of 294 utterances in the 2022 SONA, President Marcos Jr. spoke most dominantly in the Assertive Illocutionary 197 times, while in the 2023 SONA, he spoke most dominantly in the Assertive Illocutionary 222 out of 283 utterances. The least used Illocutionary Speech Act Classification for the 2022 and 2023 SONA is the Declaration Classification accounting for only 1 utterance out of 294 in 2022 SONA and 1 out of 283 utterances in 2023 SONA. The result implies that in the 2022 and 2023 SONA, the President's main intention was to Assert. Despite his utterances of Commissives, Expressives, Directives, and Declarations, his primary intention in the 2 SONAs is to Assert or present information, facts, plans, statements, and opinions. That, in turn, leads to the conclusion of the study that President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. is an Assertive Speaker. Researchers can build on this conclusion, conducting further studies on the Illocutionary Speech Acts used on the forthcoming SONAs of the current Philippine President throughout his term, to create in the future a complete analysis of the Illocutionary Speech Acts used on all the 6 SONAs of President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr.

Keywords: *speech act theory, speech act, illocutionary speech acts, discourse analysis method, state of the nation address*

Introduction

A speech is a form or mode of communication used to convey a message, information, and opinion to an audience. It is in business, education, and entertainment, but most commonly in politics.

Declared as the president-elect last May 25, 2022, and took seat on June 30, 2022, the Philippine 17th President, Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr., has already made two State of the Nation addresses. The first SONA was given last July 25, 2022, and the second was given last July 24, 2023. The State of the Nation Address (SONA) is a fundamental duty and annual tradition wherein the president reports on the nation's status, announces the government's agenda for the coming year, and proposes specific legislative measures to Congress (Presidential Communications Office, 2023).

SONAs, as stated by Sigelman (1996), cited by Adjie et al. (2015), is the speech that shapes how people understand the system of governance on both the theoretical and functional levels. The speech is a form of rhetoric where presidents remember their nation's past, envision the future, and try to set the tomorrow for the following years in office while focusing on the present (Sigelman, 1996). The objective of a given speech can be identified through its communicative function, which is produced through the kind of speech acts performed (Trosborg, 2000).

This is where Speech Acts come into the discussion. Dylgeri (2017) stated that political discourse is a complex human activity that deserves critical study, mainly because of its central place in the organization and management of society. Since a politician's speech is mainly about persuading or making others believe what one is saying, the Speech Acts play the most crucial role (Dylgeri, 2017). It presents and records some of the significant Illocutionary Acts that convey the intention of speakers in political speeches (Dylgeri, 2017). In this area, the speech act analysis of political speeches provides the understanding that political leaders perform various acts through their speeches (Hashim, 2015). Praditya et al. (2014) stated that the speech act theory reveals how speakers express and deliver their purposes using utterances.

Asadu (2013) states that the Illocutionary Act refers to what someone does in saying something because Illocutionary force is the speaker's intent addressed to the hearer. As Dylgeri (2017) expressed, Illocutionary Acts convey speakers' intentions in political speeches. Hashim (2015) identified the Illocutionary Act as the explicit performative, that is, the conventional force achieved in the saying of that utterance; this is realized, according to Austin (1962), as the successful realization of the speaker's intention, which for Searle (1969) is a product of the listener's interpretation.

Wardana et al. (2019), citing Searle (1969), classified the Illocutionary Speech Act into five kinds of utterance, each with a communicative function. The five forms of speech that showed the form function can be summarized as assertive, directive, expressive, commissive, and declaration. Assertive is the form said that binds speakers to the truth of a proposition disclosed; Directives is the

form of speech intended for speakers to create the effect that the hearer take actions; Expressive is a form of discourse that presents to express the psychological attitudes of speakers towards a situation; Commissive is the nature of speech that serves to express a promise or offer; Declaration is the form of discourse utterances linking content with the fact (Searle, 1969).

Analyzing Illocutionary Speech Acts in political speeches enables the researchers to understand what kind of speaker a politician may be. Many studies have already been done concerning the Illocutionary Speech Acts of the Political Speeches of Presidents, either in SONAs or Inaugural Speeches or speeches as a whole. However, no study has yet been done specifically on the Illocutionary Speech Acts used in the 2022 and 2023 SONA of President Marcos Jr.

Research Questions

This study aimed to understand what kind of speaker President Marcos Jr. is by analyzing the Illocutionary Speech Acts used in his 2022 and 2023 State of the Nation Address by answering the questions:

1. What Illocutionary Speech Acts were used by President Marcos Jr. in the 2022 and 2023 SONA, and what are their classifications?
2. What is the most dominant Illocutionary Speech Act used and the least used by President Marcos Jr. in his 2022 and 2023 SONA?

Literature Review

Lupas and Muica (2022) stated that by analyzing the Illocutionary Acts of the two SONAs, the majority of Duterte's speeches are Representative (61.95%) while the Declarations are the least, which only account for 0.21 % of all utterances. Through the study of speech acts, President Duterte focuses more on representatives, essentially the utterance of simple statements.

Wardana et al. (2019) stated that by analyzing the President's Speech, the researcher can then prove whether the speech contains Perlocutionary Acts of insult or not. It is done by utilizing Searle's theory on Illocutionary Acts. By analyzing the Speech acts of the selected speech, insult can be determined even when done with subtlety.

Prasetyo (2017) stated from his study, after analyzing the Illocutionary Acts in the selected speech, the dominant types of Illocutionary Acts were Exertives (used to warn or advise citizens to save the unity of his country of America), behaviors (used to give more attention and affection towards his citizen), and Commissives (used to ensure the citizens, especially the Muslim American that Obama as always in their side). Illocutionary Acts can provide a deeper understanding of what the speaker has in mind as he or she directs his or her speech toward his or her intended purpose. Wiratama (2017) stated that by analyzing twenty-four pieces of data on Illocutionary Acts that were used by Donald Trump, the most prominent type is Representative. That shows that President Donald Trump likes to simplify statements, and simplification leads to understatements.

Another study focusing on Trump's political speech is the study of Vinni (2021), wherein by Illocutionary Speech Act analysis, the type produced by Trump was the assertive type. In another related study, Auliya (2017) also concluded that by performing assertively, Trump wants to convince people to believe in his statements and to vote for him as the next president of the United States of America. As a result of the Illocutionary Speech Act analysis of a speech by Donald Trump, Rahman and Mufiah (2019) concluded that Donald Trump is primarily an assertive speaker, for he asserts to the audience what the nation will be.

In another study by Ramadhani et al. (2019) on a speech of Donald Trump, through analysis, Trump's political speech is a statement of assertion and fact where he attempts to represent himself and convince citizens with facts about the problem that he believes to be the case to establish a positive image toward his arguments. Larasati et al. (2020) concluded in their Illocutionary Speech Acts analysis of Trump's Presidential Candidacy Speech that he mainly produced the assertive type of Illocutionary Acts in his speech.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the discourse analysis method, a qualitative research type. It is a contemporary approach emphasizing human language as a socially contextual performance (Wertz et al., 2011). It is a hypernym for describing approaches examining discourses related to specific social contexts. Such analysis means scanning how language operates and how meaning develops in different social interactions. It centers on the social aspects of communication and how people use language to attain specific effects. By analyzing the context by transcribing the speeches and identifying patterns, themes, and trends, the speeches were examined by the frequency, types, and implications of these Illocutionary Speech acts. Objective answers were then obtained, answering the questions as to what Illocutionary Speech acts were used and the most dominant classification used in the two SONAs.

Procedure

The Discourse Analysis Method of Wertz et al. (2011), grounded in the Speech Act Theory of Austin (1962) and Searle (1969), structured the process into Analysis, Categorization, and Assessment.

First, in the Analysis, the researchers immersed themselves in the data by first reading the whole transcript of the 2022 and 2023 SONA 3 times. Since the researchers are comprised of two, one was assigned to the 2022 and 2023 SONA. Each researcher read the SONA

from start to finish and then analyzed the whole transcript of each SONA, to identify the Illocutionary Speech Acts used in the two SONAs.

Second, the Analysis and Categorization went hand in hand together. As the researchers analyzed to identify the Illocutionary Speech Acts used in the utterances of the two SONAs, to ensure accuracy, they categorized the utterances to their accurate classifications through the 5 Illocutionary Speech Acts Classifications of Austin (1962) and Searle (1969) which are Assertive (Stating, Suggesting, Boasting, Complaining, Claiming, Describing); Directive (Ordering, Commanding, Requesting, Recommending); Expressive (Thanking, Praising, Welcoming); Commissive (Promising, Threatening); Declaration (Declaring, Dismissing).

To easily identify the data, the researchers employed this coding system which for Assertive are Claiming (CM), Complaining (CP), Stating (ST), Boasting (BT), Describing (DB), and Suggesting (SU); for Directive are Ordering (OR), Requesting (RQ), Commanding (CG), and Recommending (RM); for Commissive are Promising (PM) and Threatening (TT); for Expressive are Thanking (TK), Welcoming (WC), and Praising (PR); and for Declaration are Declaring (DC) and Dismissing (DS). For the SONA they belong to, the researchers employed code 22 for the 2022 SONA and code 23 for the 2023 SONA.

The last step was the Assessment. The researchers tallied the findings to create summary tables for each SONA from the results of the Analysis and Categorization. They assessed the summary tables and compared the two tables to identify the differences and similarities, to formulate the conclusion from all the data gathered. The researchers then formulated their conclusion, answered the research problem, and concluded the study.

Results

In this section, the researchers present the results of their data gathering and analysis of the 2022 and 2023 SONA of President Marcos Jr.

Table 1. 2022 SONA Analysis Result

<i>Illocutionary Classifications</i>	<i>2022 SONA - 294 Utterances</i>
Assertive	Total – 197
• Stating	112
• Suggesting	20
• Boasting	3
• Describing	62
Directive	Total – 25
• Ordering	1
• Commanding	11
• Requesting	1
• Recommending	12
Commissive	Total – 59
• Promising	59
Expressive	Total – 12
• Thanking	3
• Praising	7
• Welcoming	2
Declaration	Total – 1
• Declaring	1

Table 2. 2023 SONA Analysis Result

<i>Illocutionary Classifications</i>	<i>2023 SONA - 283 Utterances</i>
Assertive	Total – 222
• Stating	154
• Claiming	12
• Boasting	40
• Describing	14
• Complaining	1
• Suggesting	1
Directive	Total – 14
• Requesting	8
• Commanding	2
• Recommending	4
Commissive	Total – 30
• Promising	29
• Threatening	1
Expressive	Total – 16
• Thanking	3

• Welcoming	1
• Praising	12
Declaration	Total – 1
• Dismissing	1

These are the Illocutionary Speech Acts identified with one classification sample that represents the whole, with the explanation of why they belong to this classification sample and classification.

Searle (1969) states that every classification has their classification samples which is the signifier of why they belong to that specific classification. We present the identified classification samples under each of the identified Illocutionary Speech Acts classifications from the two SONAs.

4.1 Assertive Illocutionary Classification

Assertive is the form that binds speakers to the truth of a statement expressed (Searle, 1969).

4.1.1 Assertive Illocutionary Classification: Stating

The first kind of Assertive is Stating (ST), which is the utterance of telling or expressing information (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“I come before you today to address you, as it is my duty as President of the Republic.”- ST 22.1

Right after his courtesy to the audience, the statement in ST 22.1 follows. He informed the nation that “it is my duty as President of the Republic” of his job. He stated, “I come before you today to address you,” informing the nation of the reason why he was standing in front of them.

For the 2023 SONA:

“Let me now report to the people on the successes that we can now lay claim to, and also the challenges that we continue to face.”- ST 23.2

In the ST 23.2, as he opened his 2023 SONA, the President stated his intention to express to the people the information (Searle, 1969) to which he reports “the success” that we as a nation can claim and “also the challenges that we” as a nation continue to face.

4.1.2 Assertive Illocutionary Classification: Boasting

Another kind of assertive is Boasting (BT) which is the utterance of speaking proudly about what one has done or what one owns (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“More than a million names have already graduated from the list. And I am glad to know that they are now standing on their own feet.”- BT 22.1

In BT 22.1, the utterance inside the bracket is the original transcript. It was translated from the Filipino language to English for better elaboration. In the utterance, the president speaks proudly of the achievements his administration has made. Referring to the transparent 4Ps beneficiary list, he mentioned before this:

“In order to ensure that qualified families receive government assistance through the 4Ps or Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program, we will ensure a clean beneficiary list.” (SONA, 2022)

The president boasted of what he achieved – allowing a million names to “graduate” from the list, signifying that those individuals can now provide for their own by providing a clean beneficiary list.

For the 2023 SONA:

“We have created nearly four thousand additional fabrication labs, production, and cold storage facilities that are available to all.”- BT 23.7.3

In BT 23.7.3, the President also spoke proudly of what he and his administration has done (Searle, 1969) by boasting of big numbers in the phrase “created nearly four thousand additional fabrication labs”.

4.1.3 Assertive Illocutionary Classification: Claiming

The next kind of Assertive is Claiming (CM) which is the utterance to say that something is true or fact, although you cannot prove it and other people might not believe it (Searle, 1969).

Only the 2023 SONA had this classification sample:

“The “One Grid, One Market” will enable more efficient transfers and more competitive pricing of electricity throughout the country.”- CM 23.5

The utterance CM 23.5 followed this utterance:

“We finally have a Unified National Grid, with the interconnection of the Luzon, Visayas, and Mindanao grid,” (SONA, 2023);

The President then claimed that this “Unified National Grid” or “One Grid, One Market will enable more efficient transfers” all over the nation despite saying that there are “68 grid connections” still delayed and that they are still “conducting a performance review”, implying that the claim of “more efficient transfers” is still not proven to be true (Searle, 1969) as seen in the utterance that followed it:

“However, 68 grid connections are much delayed, according to the ERC’s count. We are conducting a performance review of our private concessionaire, the National Grid Corporation of the Philippines,” (SONA, 2023)

4.1.4 Assertive Illocutionary Classification: Suggesting

Another kind of Assertive is Suggesting (SU) which is the utterance of mentioning an idea, plan, or action for others to consider (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“We need a new breed of farmers equipped with modern agricultural technology able to engage in sustained scientific farming that will not only increase farm yields, but also resilience in the face of climate change.” – SU 22.1

In SU 22.1, he suggests the idea that there is a “need,” which tells the level of importance of something that he mentions to his audience, allowing them to reconsider his statement. A need for a “new breed of farmers equipped with modern agricultural technology able to engage in sustained scientific farming,” and supporting his suggestion with its purpose of “will increase not only farm yields but also resilience in the face of climate change.”

For the 2023 SONA:

“If necessary we will even do cloud-seeding to bring rain.”- SU 23.1

SU 23.1 is classified as a Suggesting utterance under the Assertive Illocutionary Classification because of how it is structured. The phrase “if necessary” shows the President’s intention to offer or mention an idea to be considered by others (Searle, 1969), because only if it is necessary, then, as how the President said, “we will even do cloud-seeding to bring rain”. The President indicates with the pronoun “we” that he and his administration will offer to make this action (Searle, 1969), only if necessary. He is clearly suggesting.

4.1.5 Assertive Illocutionary Classification: Complaining

The next kind of Assertive is Complaining (CP) which is the utterance of saying that something is wrong or not satisfactory (Searle, 1969).

Only the 2023 SONA had this classification sample”

“Their work is simply not right and it is not compatible with our good purpose. They are doing fraud.”- CP 23.1

CP 23.1 is classified as a Complaining utterance under the Assertive Illocutionary Classification because of the words used by the President which indicates his dissatisfaction. The phrases “simply not right” and “not compatible with our good purpose” “show the President’s complaint. These phrases indicate negativity because the President thinks that what “they” do is wrong (Searle, 1969). The pronoun “they” refers to the “smugglers” and “hoarders” as he uttered in the utterance that came before it, saying:

“One of the reasons for the price increase is the smugglers, and hoarders who manipulated the prices of agricultural products” (SONA, 2023);

It is because of the “smugglers” and “hoarders” that the President then said this complaining utterance, to which he finished with “They are doing fraud”. The word “Fraud” is likewise negative.

4.1.6 Assertive Illocutionary Classification: Describing

The last kind of Assertive is Describing (DB) which is the utterance of telling the form characteristic, state, or purpose of someone or something (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“The Philippines has always been open and welcoming to all our foreign friends and visitors. That is our world view, that is our culture.” – DB 22.41

In DB 22.41, the characteristics are uttered. Signifying that the “Philippines,” which is our country “has always been open and

welcoming to all our foreign friends and visitors.” Describing the nature of the Filipinos, he supported his description with “That is our world view, that is our culture,” – that characteristic is already in our nature and within innate.

For the 2023 SONA:

“In our world with scarce resources, the circular economy allows us to fully use these resources, minimize waste, and reduce the need for new resources—just as it is in nature.”- DB 23.11

DB 23.11 is classified as describing because after its opening phrase of “in a world with scarce resources”, the President then described how “the circular economy” allows us to fully use these resources, “minimize waste” and “reduce the need for new resources”. He described how the form (Searle, 1969) of this economy, the Circular Economy, benefits the nation.

4.2 Directive Illocutionary Classification

Directive is the utterance or form of speech intended for speakers to create the effect that the hearer takes action (Searle, 1969).

4.2.1 Directive Illocutionary Classification: Requesting

The first kind of Directive is Requesting (RQ) which is the utterance of officially asking politely for something (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“We continue to encourage everyone to get their booster shots in preparation for the resumption of in-person classes.” – RQ 22.1

The utterance is classified as requesting under the Directive Illocutionary Classification because it is in the form of a request. The president used the pronoun “We” referring to himself and his administration, “continue” so it is not only at that moment that they have taken the action, but was already being done before the 2022 SONA happened. The president the pronoun “Everyone” to address all of the people in the country. This request of the president is uttered in preparation of the “resumption of in-person classes.

For the 2023 SONA:

“We therefore seek once again the continued support of Congress to enact into law the policies and reforms under our fiscal framework.”- RQ 23.1

RQ 23.1 begins with the pronoun “we” which refers to the President and his administration, and the emphasis of request is in the phrase “seek once again” because the President officially asked politely for (Searle, 1969) “the continued support of the Congress” for President Marcos Jr.’s administration to “enact into the law the policies and reforms” under his term.

4.2.2 Directive Illocutionary Classification: Commanding

Another kind of Directive is Commanding (CG) which is the utterance that has the authority to give orders (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“My order to the Department of Transportation or DOTR is really very simple: FULL SPEED AHEAD!” – CG 22.7

In CG 22.7, the command is already evident because of the term “My order,” which fits into Searle’s definition of Commanding. The president used an idiomatic expression “FULL SPEED AHEAD!” pertaining to moving as fast as possible or starting right away relating the phrase to the sector he mentioned before, which is the Department of Transportation. This phrase is all in uppercase signifying that the president emphasized the matter.

For the 2023 SONA:

“Consistent with this transformative policy direction, all government offices must then ensure that their vital services are digitalized immediately.”- CG 23.1

CG 23.1 is classified as Commanding under the Directive Illocutionary Classification because the President made the directive utterance of creating the effect for the hearer to take action (Searle, 1969), specifically for “all government offices” the order that they “must ensure that their vital services are digitalized immediately” in line with the President’s “transformative policy direction”. The emphasis of it as a commanding utterance is seen with the use of the word “immediately”, indicating that this command of his must be done now.

4.2.3 Directive Illocutionary Classification: Ordering

The next kind of Directive is Ordering (OR) which is the utterance to request to make, supply, or deliver food, goods, or something (Searle, 1969).

Only the 2022 SONA had this classification sample:

“Let’s make sure that there are enough funds for the nearly seventy residential care centers and seven non-residential care centers for

the vulnerable sectors and persons with disabilities who take shelter here.” – OR 22.1

The utterance is classified as Ordering under the Directive Illocutionary Classification, and it is structured in the form of a request. According to Searle (1969), order is an utterance to request to make, supply, etc. In this utterance, although there is no evident term “order,” the phrase “Let’s make sure that there are enough funds,” pertaining that “Let us” is everyone, the president is requesting everyone for this matter. An order to sustain the funds for the “vulnerable sections and persons with disabilities” – the ones who are given less attention by others.

4.2.4 Directive Illocutionary Classification: Recommending

Another kind of directive is Recommending (RM) which is the utterance to suggest that someone or something would be more suitable for a job or purpose or that a particular action should be taken (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“The condition and availability of school rooms for our students must also be addressed, again, in coordination with the Department of Public Works and Highways.” – RM 22.4

In RM 22.4, the President addresses the “condition and availability of school rooms” of “our students,” referring to Filipino students. He added that it is “in coordination with” a particular sector or someone suitable for this job, according to Searle (1969). The president recommends that a specific action and sector, the “Department of Public Works and Highways,” act.

For the 2023 SONA:

“Our efforts must not be scattershot, but rather, cohesive, centralized, and systematic.” RM 23.2

RM 23.2 begins with the pronoun “our” as said by the President and refers to the President, his administration, and all listeners. As the President refers to “our”, “our efforts must not be scattershot” – the words that follow convey the President’s recommendation that this particular action should also be taken (Searle, 1969) or done.

4.3 Commissive Illocutionary Classification

Commissive is the form of expressing a promise or offer (Searle, 1969).

4.3.1 Commissive Illocutionary Classification: Promising

The first kind of Commissive is Promising (PM) which is the utterance when the speaker promises to do a future action to the benefit of a hearer (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“Tax compliance procedures will be simplified to promote ease of paying taxes.”- PM 22.6

In PM 22.6, specifically “Tax compliance procedures will be simplified” the President, upon the utterance of it, promises and promotes “ease” in paying taxes. Having said that his audience is the people of the nation, this matter is for their benefit.

For the 2023 SONA:

“To complete this reintegration process, I will issue a Proclamation granting amnesty to rebel returnees.”- PM 23.14

PM 23.14 starts with the intention which is “to complete this reintegration process”, then it is followed by the pronoun “I” which refers to the President, and again, the verb “will” which indicates a future act – that the President “will issue a Proclamation granting amnesty to rebel returnees”, which again is a future action to the benefit of (Searle, 1969) or promise by President Marcos Jr. to the rebel returnees.

4.3.2 Commissive Illocutionary Classification: Threatening

Another kind of Commissive is Threatening (TT) which is the utterance committing to taking future action against the addressee (Searle, 1969).

Only the 2023 SONA had a Threatening Classification Sample:

“The days of those smugglers and hoarders are numbered.”- TT 23.1

TT 23.1 is classified as a Threatening Classification Sample under the Commissive Illocutionary Classification because the utterance is structured in the form of a threat. The words “the days of those” are structured in a way that an action will be done to stop them for it is then followed by “smugglers and hoarders” and ending with “are numbered” – this structure of the sentence expresses that their days, the smugglers and hoarders, are coming to an end for the president is committing to take future action against (Searle, 1969) them which is a threatening utterance.

4.4 Expressive Illocutionary Classification

Expressive is the form that expresses the psychological attitude of a speaker towards a condition (Searle, 1969).

4.4.1 Expressive Illocutionary Classification: Thanking

The first kind of expressive is Thanking (TK) which is the utterance expressing to someone that one is pleased about or is grateful for something they have done (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“We are, in fact, grateful for the messages of support and offers of help that we have received from many of our friends in the international community.” – TK 22.2

TK 22.2 also expresses gratification for the “messages of support and offers of help” from his “friend in the international community.” Attempting it to be sincere by adding “We are, in fact,” at the beginning of the utterance.

For the 2023 SONA:

“On behalf of these farmers and their families, thank you again to our legislators.”- TK 23.2

TK 23.2 followed the utterance:

“Because of this, the 57 billion pesos debt borne by more than six hundred thousand beneficiaries has been completely erased” (SONA, 2023);

That is why he thanked the legislators on behalf of the farmers for making that possible.

4.4.2 Expressive Illocutionary Classification: Welcoming

Another kind of Expressive is Welcoming (WC) which is the utterance expressing courtesy to someone (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“Vice President Sara Zimmerman Duterte; Former Presidents Joseph Ejercito Estrada, Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo and Rodrigo Roa Duterte; Senate President Juan Miguel Zubiri and the honorable members of the Senate; House Speaker Ferdinand Martin Romualdez and the honorable members of the House of Representatives; Chief Justice Alexander Gesmundo and the honorable Justices of the Supreme Court; the Apostolic Nuncio Most Reverend Charles John Brown and the esteemed members of the diplomatic corps; the honorable members of the Cabinet; our First Lady Louise Araneta-Marcos and our children [applause]; distinguished guests; my beloved countrymen; ladies and gentlemen; good afternoon to all of you.” – WC 22.1

WC 22.1 is the first utterance that the President uttered in his first SONA after he was introduced. He greeted and mentioned the prominent political people, his family, his countrymen, and everyone during the 2022 SONA.

For the 2023 SONA, here is the only welcoming utterance:

“Allow me to greet Vice President Sara Zimmerman Duterte; the former Presidents – our former Presidents, President Joseph Ejercito Estrada and President Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo; Senate President Juan Miguel Zubiri and the Honorable Members of the Senate; House Speaker Ferdinand Martin Romualdez and the Honorable Members of the House of Representatives; Chief Justice Alexander Gesmundo and the Honorable Justices of the Supreme Court; His Excellency, Most Reverend Charles John Brown and the esteemed members of the Diplomatic Corps; Executive Secretary Lucas Bersamin and the members of the Cabinet; First Lady Louise Araneta-Marcos; former First Lady, First Lady Imelda Romualdez Marcos; other distinguished guests; my beloved countrymen; ladies and gentlemen, good afternoon to everyone.”- WC 23.1

WC 23.1 came after the very first utterance of “thanking” by the President after he was introduced and was called to speak. The way it was structured, calling on and greeting the distinguished guests and people present in his 2023 SONA, as well as his beloved countrymen, ending it with a courteous greeting of “good afternoon” are all an expression of courtesy according to Searle (1969) towards the people as he then opened his 2023 SONA.

4.4.3 Expressive Illocutionary Classification: Praising

The last kind of Expressive is Praising (PR) which is expressing admiration or approval for the achievement or characteristic of a person or a thing (Searle, 1969).

For the 2022 SONA:

“The creativity of the Filipino is truly world-class.”- PK 22.1

In PK 22.1 President showed admiration with the “creativity” of the Filipino and praising it as “truly world class” in the field of arts, culture, and etc. which he uttered after it:

“We excel in arts and culture, new media, live events — avenues which generate primary and downstream jobs for our creative and talented countrymen.” (SONA, 2022)

For the 2023 SONA:

“We are proud of the progress that the BARMM has taken. It will be self-governing, it will be progressive, and it will be effective.”- PR 23.10

PR 23.10 uses the word “proud”, with the pronoun “we” implying that the President and his administration are expressing their admiration towards the progress of the BARMM. It was then followed by the President’s continual approval of what BARMM has progressed to - self-governing, progressive, and effective.

4.5 Declaration Illocutionary Classification

Declaration is the form connecting content with fact (Searle, 1969). It is the utterance of changing reality in accord with the proposition.

4.5.1 Declaration Illocutionary Classification: Declaring

The first kind of Declaration is Declaring (DC) which is the utterance of changing the state of something in an immediate way (Searle, 1969).

Only the 2022 SONA has this classification sample:

“Expenditure priorities will be realigned, and spending efficiency will be improved to immediately address the economic scarring arising from the effects of COVID-19, and also to prepare for future shocks.” – DC 22.1

DC 22.1 is considered as a Declaration because it refers to the statement "Expenditure priorities will be realigned, and spending efficiency will be improved immediately." The terms "realigned" and "improved" indicate a change in the state of expenditure priorities and spending efficiency. The adverb "immediately" emphasizes the urgency of the matter. The statement that follows, "address the economic scarring arising from the effects of COVID-19, and also to prepare for future shocks," is classified as an Assertive statement and only supports the previous statement.

4.5.2 Declaration Illocutionary Classification: Dismissing

The last kind of Declaration is Dismissing (DS) which is the utterance deciding that something or someone is not relevant and not worth considering (Searle, 1969).

Only the 2023 SONA has this classification sample:

“I will be accepting their resignations.”- DS 23.1

DS 23.1 is classified as Dismissing because in the utterance, “I” represents the President, who is the head of the nation and has the authority to give or take away government position. The phrase “will be” represents the President’s intent to fulfill his decision, the decision of dismissing “Unscrupulous law enforcers” from the utterance that came before it:

“Unscrupulous law enforcers and others involved in the highly nefarious drug trade have been exposed.” (SONA, 2023);

Dismissing them by “accepting their resignations”. The word “Resignation” aligns with Searle’s Resigning Classification Sample under the Declaration Illocutionary Classification, which is giving up a role or position by telling your employer you are leaving (Searle, 1969).

Table 3. Comparison of 2022 and 2023 SONA Analysis Result

Illocutionary Classifications	2022 SONA – 294 Utterances	2023 SONA – 283 Utterances
Assertive	Total – 197	Total – 222
• Stating	112	154
• Claiming	0	12
• Boasting	3	40
• Describing	62	14
• Complaining	0	1
• Suggesting	20	1
Directive	Total – 25	Total – 14
• Requesting	1	8
• Commanding	11	2
• Ordering	1	0
• Recommending	12	4
Commissive	Total – 59	Total – 30
• Promising	59	29
• Threatening	0	1

Expressive	Total – 12	Total – 16
• Thanking	3	3
• Welcoming	2	1
• Praising	7	12
Declaration	Total – 1	Total – 1
• Dismissing	0	1
• Declaring	1	0

Now in comparing the data gathered from the analysis of the 2022 and 2023 SONA of Philippine President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr., it is clear that in both SONAs, the most dominant Illocutionary Speech Act used by the President was the Assertive Illocutionary Classification. When it comes to the least used, both SONAs are the same, for they both have the Declaration Illocutionary Classification as their least used Illocutionary Speech Act Used, accounting to 1 out of 294 utterances in the 2022 SONA and 1 as well out of 283 utterances in the 2023 SONA.

The difference in degree can also be seen in comparing the 2 SONAs. In the 2022 SONA, he has more statements uttered, which is to be expected, considering that 2022 is the beginning of his term, so it is time for him to lay out his plans. Compared to the 2023 SONA, more praises and boasting utterances are uttered, considering that he is then showcasing what he and his administration have done in his 1-year term as President of the Philippines. He gave more directions in his 2022 SONA than his 2023 SONA and even more promises, for again, he was still starting to outline his plans for the nation.

In the two SONAs, despite his utterances of Commissives, Expressives, Directives, and Declarations, his primary intention was to assert or present information, opinions, plans, facts, and statements.

Discussion

The SONA is indeed a speech which is used to accomplish different goals or ends in different circumstances (Medhurst, 2010), and in the results of the study, the goal of the President was to make Assertive utterances or to present or assert statements, information, facts, and opinions. That is evidently clear from the results of the analysis since it is the most dominant communicative force (Yule, 1996) and conventional force (Hashim, 2015) used - it is the most dominantly used Illocutionary Speech Act Classification by President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. in his 2022 and 2023 State of the Nation Address.

Just as Lupas and Muica (2022) concluded that President Duterte was an Assertive Speaker in his two SONAs through their analysis of the Illocutionary Speech Acts used by the President; and as Prasetyo (2017) also concluded that President Obama was primarily a Directive Speaker with his Illocutionary Speech Act Analysis of the President's speeches; and Wiratama (2017), Rahman and Mufiah (2019), and Vinni (2021) all concluding that President Trump was also an Assertive Speaker through their Illocutionary Speech Acts Analysis of the President's speeches; in the same manner from the results of the data gathered from the 2022 and 2023 SONA Illocutionary Speech Act Analysis result through Discourse Analysis (Wertz et al., 2011), all implies that President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. in his two most recent SONAs, had the intention primarily to make Assertive Utterances. From all of this data, it is safe to say that President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. is an Assertive Speaker.

Conclusion

The study's findings conclude that the primary intention of Philippine President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. in his 2022 and 2023 State of the Nation Address was to assert or make Assertive utterances. Despite his utterances of Commissives, Expressives, Directives, and Declarations, his primary intention in the 2 SONAs was to assert or present information, facts, plans, statements, and opinions. That, in turn, leads to the conclusion of the study that the Philippine President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. is an Assertive type of speaker.

Researchers and Linguistic Students can conduct further research on the forthcoming SONAs of the current Philippine President throughout his term, continuing on this study to create in the future a complete analysis of the Illocutionary Speech Acts used on all the 6 State of the Nation Addresses of President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. Researchers can also build further on this, conducting further studies on the Illocutionary Speech Acts used, not just on SONAs but also on other Political Speeches of Presidents and Politicians in the Philippines.

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